

The Square as a Reflection of Urban Identity: The Example of Palavra Square

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Abstract

Squares serve as dynamic spaces that play a significant role in shaping and reflecting daily life within cities. They act as stationary points, gathering urban interests and contributing to the characterization of a city. Palavra Square, also known as Cumhuriyet Square, located in Tunceli, holds particular importance as a meeting place where people gather, engage in political discussions, share cultural experiences, and form collective memories. This study employs a phenomenological design to explore the relationship between space and urban identity, focusing on Palavra Square as a prime example. The research methodology involves semi-structured interviews conducted with four residents of Tunceli who have experienced the dynamics of Palavra Square. Additionally, document analysis is employed to gather information from books, comments, and memories associated with the square. By studying the dimensions of self in relation to urban space, conscious and unconscious complex ideas, emotions, values, goals, preferences, skills, and behavioral tendencies that define an individual's personal identity are explored. Palavra Square serves as a multifaceted space that encompasses various functions and meanings. Beyond being a platform for political and economic discussions, the square symbolizes collective memory production. Its historical significance fosters a sense of continuity with the past, preserving group traditions that contribute to the urban identity of Tunceli. Furthermore, the square's association with theatrical exaggeration tradition adds to its cultural significance, further ingraining it in the city's identity. The findings of this study shed light on how Palavra Square shapes the urban identity of Tunceli. By understanding the interplay between space and personal identity, this research contributes to the broader discourse on urban sociology and the significance of public squares as essential elements of city life.

Keywords; City, Identity, Square, Tunceli, Palavra Square

The Role of Palavra Square in Shaping Urban Identity: A Phenomenological Study

Spaces bear traces of societies and rituals at various times. Cities, times, and societies have their own spatial identity. The space-individual relationship has an identity quality. Space, which has an individual definition, is also social. "Space" is the social space in which we live and relate to others. Space organizes things, makes arrays, or distributes them. George Simmel, in the sociology of space, discussed concepts such as the urbanization process

and the separation of space in modern societies, and talked about the individual effects of space. Space in Sociology has been discussed and grounded by theorists such as Michel Foucault, Henri Lefebvre, David Harvey, Manuel Castells, Martina Löw, and Edward Soja. Foucault's studies on prisons, asylums, and heterotopias are especially important in the sociology of space. Marxist space theorists, Lefebvre (2014), Harvey (2022), Castells (2005), Soja (2019), produced theories on the structural, capitalist, global, and homogenization-based features of spaces. Martina Löw (2016) conceptualized space as a social phenomenon. Löw (2016) explains space as a basic sociological concept to be used as a tool of interaction and as an analytical element in the study of social reality.

The discussion of space concepts in sociological thought is dominated by physical perspectives. It is argued that, in the era of globalization and mediatization, the concept of space can only be comprehended based on a relativist understanding (Löw, 2016, p. 32). Löw (2016, p. 36) critically reflects on fundamental work in sociology, particularly urban sociology, and reviews Georg Simmel's essay on "The Sociology of Space." It is evident that space is often reified as a region, and the distinction between space and place is not always made, resulting in an absolutized perception of space. The complete mediatization of life through new communication technologies renders space both virtual and global. Globalization processes connect distant places, transforming them into spaces that can simultaneously encompass multiple intervals in one location. Even the human body is no longer experienced as a closed container space but as an open system. Löw (2016) demonstrates that space cannot be solely understood as a relational arrangement determined by social relations. Sociological analysis involves understanding how spaces emerge, embody, and undergo change, as well as how they structure society and who participates in their organization and formation. Space is described as a relational arrangement of social goods and living things within spaces (Löw, 2016, p. 96). It emerges through the interaction of action and structure, resulting in the placement of people, social goods, and cultural signs to create spatial arrangements. The act of synthesis enables individuals to perceive, imagine, and remember the spatial placement of people and social goods consistently and reliably (Harvey, 2022; Lefebvre, 2014; Löw, 2016). The reproduction of institutionalized spaces occurs through repetition in daily routines (Lefebvre, 2014; Löw, 2016). Space is intertwined with cultural, class, and gender concepts. Spatial and temporal structures are both forms of social structure. Spaces produce distributions in a hierarchically organized society, often supporting unequal or diverse groups of people (Harvey, 2022; Löw, 2016, p. 96). Atmospheres are external effects of social elements and individuals on spatial arrangements, influencing how individuals feel at home or strange in particular spaces (Löw, 2016, p. 108). Space organizes and defines the individual, while the individual also organizes and reproduces space in a relational manner. In sociology, there are functionalist, critical, interactionist, post-modern, and feminist approaches to space. Space can be understood as historically contingent social processes occurring in a given space. It is intricately intertwined with power geometries and experienced differently by different people.

In the sociology of space, the relationship between space and individuals, or between the city and its inhabitants, can be understood through social analysis. The notion of place or city is intertwined with society, individuals, and culture, signifying their connection with themselves through space within a broader context. Urban design, shaped by historical and formal city features, is a social practice. Thus, perceiving cities or places purely rationally is not possible. Consequently, the social meaning of space remains significant, contributing to why urban spaces retain their names and functions among the people despite evolving forms throughout history. Spatial forms play a crucial role in shaping urban identity. In space studies, it is essential not to overlook the individuals who interact with the space. The city, space, and identity relationship can be better understood by considering the impact of individuals on the space. Those who use, live in, produce, and are influenced by the space significantly contribute to the essence of the city. An individual's identity includes information about their origins or where they belong. Everyone in the world has a sense of belonging somewhere. While an individual's physical appearance often shapes the initial impression they make on others, this impression frequently overlaps with assumptions about their origins.

The spatial identity attributed to one place by people is constructed to separate another place. Differences between spaces are attributed or perceived by residents living inside or outside of these places. In this sense, space is a subjective social structure based on physical environments (Peng, Strijker, and Wu 2020). In this sense, the meaning of constructing the identity of a place may be related to the city in which it is found. The individual affected by it has a significant impact on the city. An individual's identity card has information about where they are from. Everyone in the world belongs somewhere. Although the first impression an individual give to others is always his or her physical appearance, such an impression often overlaps with the assumption of one's origins. The spatial identity attributed to one place by people is constructed to separate another place. Differences between spaces are attributed or perceived by residents living inside or outside of these places. In this sense, space is a subjective social structure based on physical environments (Peng, Strijker, and Wu 2020). In this sense, the meaning of constructing the identity of a place may be related to the city in which it is found. The individual affected by it has a significant impact on the city. An individual's identity card has information about where they are from. Everyone in the world belongs somewhere. Although the first impression an individual give to others is always his or her physical appearance, such an impression often overlaps with the assumption of one's origins. The spatial identity attributed to one place by people is

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As a public space, squares have an especially important sociological position. Squares are places where people meet and chat, make decisions, have fun, spread rumors, protest or approve. Squares are often the starting point of great social movements, many of them have been symbols of historical change. The squares where people discuss political, daily and economic ideas have always been tried to be controlled by the government. Because the first manifestations of many social discontents from the Middle Ages to the present; There were masses that began to gather in the squares uneasily. Squares are sometimes built by the state to set up authority, and sometimes they are formed over time with social rhythm. squares, are key areas of cities and most of them are remembered with their city squares. Taksim Square was seen as a symbol of the new government after the opening of the Republic Monument. Squares appear as a symbolic effort within the Ottoman modernization movements. 2. Abdülhamit wanted a square to be built in Beyazit so that Istanbul could become modern. Squares are a social symbol, a place where cultural production is embodied, where encounters are experienced, and where the pulse of resistance and society beats. Social memories may relate to events that occurred during our lifetime or before we were born and therefore belong to family, ethnic group, state or world history. In later cases, what we "remember" is not personal experience, but oral tradition, depends on cultural transmissions or his own motivation to do detective exploring the past. In this sense, social memories and places are intricately connected.

One of the city squares in Turkey is Palavra Square in Tunceli. Today, the area officially known as the City Square appears as a place where people sit, gather and discuss current issues on foot. Palavra Square reflects the city culture. The cultural storytelling features, discursive codes and social position of Tunceli people are identified with Palavra Square in many respects. Satire, ridicule, joking or epic narratives have a prominent place in the cultural structure of Tunceli. For this reason, Palavra Square appears as the spatial equivalent of listening to the stories that people tell seriously, political speeches, hunting memories or adventures and laughing inwardly.

Method

In the context of the sociology of space, which is a social phenomenon, the experiences, difficulties, emotions, communication styles, coping/management practices, economic and political formations of the individual and the city squares will be investigated by using qualitative research method. Qualitative research method for the discipline of sociology supplies the opportunity to collect detailed and qualified information about people's experiences, behaviors, ways of making sense of the world and world of meaning (Creswell 2021). Qualitative approach, which asserts that individuals interact with each other, produce certain meanings in the context of these interactions, and that these meanings are reinforced through interactions, is a qualitative approach, how and in which ways individuals make sense of the social world and this world, It is an appropriate research method for understanding and analyzing how they maintain existing interactions. In this study, phenomenological design was used as a qualitative research design. The phenomenological pattern is used to describe how people who have experienced a place, an event or an action feel about it and what their feelings are (Şimşek and Yıldırım 2013). One of the key features of phenomenological studies is that they allow the explanation or description of phenomena (Şimşek and Yıldırım 2013, 74). A series of semi-structured interviews were conducted on Palavra Square with individuals in the city and individuals who had experienced it, by snowball sampling. According to Silverman (2016), when the researcher encounters repetitions during qualitative research, he or she should realize that the data has reached saturation. In this sense, as a result of the fifth and sixth interviews, it was foreseen that the data should be diversified rather than the interviews, since there was no need to talk about the same discourses, not understanding why the question was asked, and not saying much about a simple phenomenon. In this sense, by making use of the flexible aspects of qualitative research, the arguments of the visual data and print media data were strengthened. In this study, in-depth interviews were conducted with four people who spent time in Palavra Square and experienced it. Known memories and feelings about the place were tried to be learned. In addition to the interviews, news, photographs, memories and historical documents about Palavra Square will be analyzed. Since there is no need to say much about a simple phenomenon, it is foreseen that it is necessary to diversify the data rather than the interviews. In this sense, by making use of the flexible aspects of qualitative research, the arguments of the

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City, Space and Public Space

In sociology, it is exceedingly difficult to define any object or conceptuality apart from subjective experiences. The urban public space or the characteristics of the individual decide what is common in this sense. Space is an active subject that interacts with the individual in daily life and has its own identity structure. While people live in spaces, they are organized, changed and included in a culture. At the same time, the individual changes their order and adds a part of himself as he passes through the space. Human and space interaction is set up through interactions in daily life. Every place creates its own people, city and lifestyle. Spaces share different time periods and gain a function related to the spirit of the period. Spaces are an important part of the image of the city as well as the spirit of the time. In this sense, space is a shared memory, cultural texture, effective in the formation of ritual forms. Examples of these places are schools, health centers, food restaurants, secure sites or squares. The design of schools, streets or squares provides us with important data about the social structure and its role in daily life. Wedding areas, cemeteries or squares appear as concrete reflections of social rituals and interactions. In this sense, the square as a space can be given as an example as a defined area shaped by the social structure. The square, which is a part of the city, culturally reflects the structure of the human being. In this sense, the square appears as an important subject, city symbol, area of interaction, area of politics, meeting, reaction area or reconciliation area in daily life.

public space: In Jurgen Habermas's *The Structural Transformation of Publicity* (Habermas 2015), it is expressed as a space in everyday life where something similar to public opinion can be created. According to Habermas (2015), public space is a free discussion space where people can take part in the discussion as equal citizens and have a say on every social, cultural and political problem. The public space has an especially prominent place in the democratic construction of social space. Public spaces appear as spaces that are produced daily, sometimes by the state, and sometimes within the routine practices of the people. According to Lefebvre, the public sphere; it is an empty cage that can have a place of transfer and transit (Lefebvre 2021, 21) through which the crowds filter themselves.

Public spaces as a spatiality where people come together to talk, chat and discuss; political, economic, cultural and sociological meaning. Since ancient times, these spaces where people come together to discuss the everyday, leaving the private, constitute the foundations of a democratic society. Individuals who come together in public spaces talk in various patterns, suspect, reassure and chat with each other. According to Goffman, the public sphere can be understood through the interrelationship patterns and networks of individuals. Goffman says that belonging and not belonging to a place can be distinguished by various elements such as dressing and speaking. Goffman explores the complexity and patterns of various forms of public relations. (Goffman 2017) discussed in his book. In the public sphere, an encounter begins and continues in many ways. The rituals of starting or ending a relationship in public spaces are regulated by various rules. These regulations; etiquette, etiquette requirements or routines and stereotyped everyday practices. Saying that it would be too easy to express that the individual plays distinct roles; he says that some things that take part in different systems of action are different things to a certain extent (Goffman 2017, 25).

In everyday life, people act in determined ways, such as regulated interactions, routine practices, customs. The variously ordered interactions and the resulting network of relations produce the social. This network of relations continues through coded or normative codes. For this reason, the continuation of daily relations is realized by the operation of these normative elements. Going beyond the normative, routine disruptive actions can be tried to be prevented by the common sense, which is public. In this sense, the public sphere also functions as a regulation. The public sphere that corrects, disciplines and sets boundaries can change and transform over time. This change in the public sphere; It stems from its characteristic of being a moment of individual and social change, where ideas open to everyone are expressed. Thinkers such as Habermas and Sennet describe that the public sphere has suffered a great destruction in this sense. The crises created by the disappearance of public spaces, which are shown as the source of many political changes in Europe, are defined by Habermas or Sennett as the

transformation of the public sphere or the collapse of the public person. In places such as shopping malls, indicators and simulations appear rather than a public space.

As medieval public spaces, squares appear as places where relationships that lead to many social changes are set up. Sennett these spaces have shown various differences today. Individuals no longer meet in the squares, but in cafes, bars, pubs or shopping centers. In encounters in such places, the individual appears as a passive element, not as an active subject. In Paris in the 1680s, he was in favor of using the squares not by encircling and taming them in Renaissance style, but by displaying the vastness of empty spaces through formal design (Sennett 2013, 81). The idea of an exceptionally large manufactured empty space in the middle of a dense urban settlement was first put forward by Parisian architects in the 1680s (Sennett 2013). While squares fulfilled a wide variety of functions in the past,

“The emerging societal problem associated with urban density was the problem of where foreigners could routinely be visible in order to form various images of foreigners. The old meeting place, the multi-purpose square, was destroyed, turning into a monumental place in Paris and a nature museum in London. Thus, the demographer was creating such an environment that he was a stranger in that environment” (Sennett 2013, 84).

Sennett criticizes desk-based theories of the public sphere, saying that “despite alarms from social psychology labs, man potentially has a real genius for being able to lead a group life in crowded conditions” (Sennett 2013, 400). Again, Sennett criticized that the planning of squares was not a secret and that it was a kind of anomaly of dead public life and perverted communal life (Sennett 2013, 401). According to Habermas, the mass media have not only been decisive in the contagious effect of worldwide cohesion. The physical presence of the masses proving in the squares and streets, unlike the 19th century and the first period of the 20th century, could only become a revolutionary force to the extent that it could be transformed into an omnipresent presence through television (Habermas 2015, 55).

The city itself is a complex phenomenon that functions at multiple economic, socio-cultural, political and environmental levels. In this sense, the city as a space is in a constant state of reaction against stimuli coming from inside or outside its borders. As a result, it can be seen that urban spaces have evolved from the comprehensive belief of individuals for their interaction and the creation of the first building masses and the articulation of the public space as a result.

Square as Space

The square, which is met as an agora in Greek cities, is completely in the form of a big street. The concept of agora in ancient Greek discourses; It has been used in different

forms such as meeting arena, market center, conversation area. According to Habermas, the public sphere was not spatially connected in antiquity (Habermas 2015, 60). During the Roman period, the squares were designed as places to watch the surrounding buildings. The square is an environment of action, management, communication, interaction and sharing, in front of everyone, that includes all individuals who have the decision power of the society they belong to, where these individuals meet, encounter, argue, fight from time to time, and make decisions together. (İnam 1998, 131). Squares are places where people can talk, stop, walk and chat with the other. Where people gather, rumors, these places where he made gossip have always been important for the government. Because the first manifestations of many social discontents from the Middle Ages to the present; There were masses that began to gather in the squares uneasily.

Lefebvre, who defines the squares as the interaction area, said that the powers cannot fully set up their sovereignty without producing space. The governments tried to change the places of the city after they took over the administration. As a result, the square is the main place where the power shows its power. For this reason, squares as a discursive space are an area of conflict. People, movements or ways of thinking actively use the squares to find a place for themselves. For this reason, the square has almost become a place of defense of different views. "Political power dominates or aims to dominate space; hence the importance of monuments and squares, but if palaces and churches have a political meaning and purpose, urban citizens divert that meaning and purpose, they appropriate this space in a non-political way. Through a certain use of time, citizens resist the state. In this way they are freed from a chain of struggle for appropriation, in which rhythms play the key role. Thus, the public sphere, that is, the space of representation, becomes the place of wanderings and encounters, of intrigues, negotiation, trade and bargaining 'in the moment', putting itself on the stage. Thus, the time and rhythms of the people in this space are reconnected to the space" (Lefebvre 2021, 131).

After the 1980s, the socialization functions of squares began to decline rapidly in Turkey and all over the world (Bilgin and Boysan 1997). Bilgin and Boysan (1997) say that in today's Turkey, cities are similar to each other, and the behavior of the 1960s and 1970s is now talked about rather than the attitudes of the cities. Squares have a soul beyond being physical spaces and have reflections on the power, ideologies and cultural values of the period (Turan and Ercoşkun 2017). In this context, the names of avenues, streets and squares have a prominent place in understanding the city.

"Private shopping malls, which have nothing to do with public space, could not always be like squares loaded with politics. The reason for the emptying of the squares was not the weather conditions, but the political atmosphere. In many of the world's cities, city squares are beginning to become places reserved for tourists, the poorest parts of the city, and even students. Obviously, there were more suitable places to read the mood of the tourists rather than the mood of the city dwellers. If an unexpected politicization does not

occur in the coming period, traffic will prevail over civilian use in the field battle. If we remember that the celebrations are no longer held in the squares, but by driving around, honking the horn or waving the flag, we can say the following:

The square is a communication space where other people are interacted with and considered. The square is also a place of memory. Memory spaces in Nora's (2006) theory are not just physical spaces. Symbolic objects such as streets or squares where stories are told, people walk, chat, joke or come together are also memory spaces (Nora 2006, 22). In this sense, cities, spaces or squares reflect social history with the abstract traces they carry. The square can be defined as subjects that convey all social networks and unwritten historicity. In this sense, squares are actually carriers of social relations. Squares are continuous formations that bring the past and present together. Discussions on the square are a memory encounter in this sense (Torlak 2016).

Bullshit Square

The most famous and largest street of the city is Cumhuriyet Caddesi. The city center was formed around this street in the late 1930s (Korkmaz 2017, 352). Its official name is "Cumhuriyet Caddesi", but those who live in the city know the place as "Bullshit". Rumor has it that the street was named "Bullshit Square" because those interested in politics walked there chattering about how to save the world (Korkmaz 2017). This ironic adjective shows the extent to which Tuncelians find daily life with politics. "Palavra" means "empty talk" in Turkish. Political conversations while walking on the street have long been an important part of daily life in Tunceli; however, the sophisticated analyzes of the street-goers don't make much sense to others. In this respect, satirical nomenclature,

Palavra Square as Entertainment and Story Space

Squares are places that concretely reflect the texture of the city, its cultural structure and how people interact with each other. Palavra Square in Tunceli has the ways of speaking, discourses, temperaments and social positions of the people here. In small cities such as Tunceli, everyone knows each other well and cannot convince anyone of their "spoils" about themselves in the community. For this reason, consistency in the stories told is especially important. However, the lies that are sometimes told for fun are listened with interest like a storytelling method. As an important storytelling narrative in Anatolian culture, "brag literature" has an especially prominent place (Sezen 2013). The people call this square, where theories, ideas, memories and future predictions are constantly discussed, Palavra Square among themselves. An Italian architect and designer Aldo Rossi (2006) defines the city as a theater stage. Palavra Square also has the elements of representation and reality as a theater space in this sense. Bullshit as a square; produces daily practices, experiences and feelings.

K1 [1] – “The people of Tunceli love to describe, they love to exaggerate, everyone without exception has this feature. The theatrical aspects are also quite developed. If you want to understand the people of Tunceli sociologically, it will be enough to visit this square and pace for a few days”.

K1- “Ma [2] I named it. Creativity. I think that people who want to come to power gave this name because the speeches they made there did not lead to a conclusion and all of them just spoke with empty words and their words did not turn into action.”

In this sense, Palavra Square is both a historical gateway and a social entity as a product of collective memory. Bragging has sometimes become a means of entertainment for people. Gathering in the square and listening to the words that he knows to be false is a common saying in Tunceli: "Tell me uncle, we like it even if it's a lie!". This definition also shows that the square is a narrative space. Telling bullshit can sometimes provide "the need for socialization, the individual and social need for heroic stories, and individual psychological relief" (Sezen 2013). In this sense, Palavra Square is the embodied spatial equivalent of the bullshit literature.

K4- “Square is equal to Tunceli. Palavra is the heart of Tunceli, it is seen as another square because it was built recently, but it is the real heart of it. Since it supplies a warm environment, there is an intimate relationship. The heart of Dersim is Palavra Square. Friendly people”

The practices of "showing off, showing off" or storytelling, which appear as a basic form of squares, are also met in Palavra Square. Palavra Square is a place to pace, stroll or play a role. They form city squares by expanding towards areas where activities are concentrated in the city. The practices of "reading around, looking around", which are among the key features of the square, appear in Palavra Square. People in all cultures have needed squares to watch each other. In this respect, squares resemble theaters; invites people to wander in that place, watch each other and wander aimlessly.

“ K2 – Tunceli open prison Palavra Square is also the courtyard, perfect for pacing. The pavement where bored, young and old people walk and save the country... It is inspiring, but important ideas come to life at these paces, these ideas are usually flimsy and therefore considered as bragging, this is how the bragging square exists. I can say that the square is identified with the province and is at the center of daily meetings and conversations”.

At the same time, the square, which can be defined as a place where people talk, teach or laugh, is the spatial equivalent of language. Language is the abstract of the existential and the concrete form of the spatial. Saying that language is the house of being, Heidegger talks about the linguistic expression of space. In this sense, it has a language in the bullshit

square. The bullshit has a language, speaks accordingly, lies and exaggerates. Palavra Square, as a spatial equivalent of the way the Tunceli dialect speaks or makes fun of it, is a place that can be silent against the other and shout within itself. Bullshit Square, like all squares, has a language and can become a foreign language for the other.

“ K1- The past is the future and the present is the time. It's more like a gathering place, with its long-standing name and the humorous bragging name. It is a public space where past grievances and future suffering are also expressed with humor. The square where the people of Dersim communicate more warmly with each other and march.”

Spatial identities are composed of city-specific spaces and values. As a reflection of the city, Palavra Square, as it consists of the unique values of Tunceli, “enables the citizens to increase their experiences through different interactions with the city, to remember the part of the city through memories, to remember the place with certain symbols, and thus to form an urban memory” (Turan and Ercoşkun 2017) .

K2- “It is an area that has not undergone much change since the city's establishment and has lived up to its name. The fact that Tunceli has a well-known representative place, which has seen many events in the past, has now become a place where people wander around empty-handed.”

K3- “Although there is no linear relationship, I actually think that it may be related to the general unemployment situation of the people of the province. It is a well-known street in terms of being in the city square. Dersim and the bragging square are essentially a whole. There is a cultural bond.”

As the collective memory of Tunceli's people, Palavra Square shapes the relationship between Tunceli and the square, as it consists of social memories as well as physical space (Turan and Ercoşkun 2017). Urban spaces are places where individuals interact with each other and convey the experience of being an urbanite to the other. Squares are a bodily part of society. People needed squares to come together, meet, consult their current issues, and create a sense of belonging.

The Memory Relationship of Space, City and Palavra Square

Tunceli's public memory can be seen in a few areas such as the city's political actors or groups, public discussion and memory spaces. The relationship between memory and space appears as a very comprehensive field in sociological terms. Space, as a concrete equivalent of memory between the past and the present, can be defined as a fixed and living social space related to the past. Squares, as a concrete equivalent of memory, are places where the traces of experiences are carried, transferred and mentioned there.

K3- "There is always a life there. It is a street that has seen many events since ancient times, where many people talked about many topics. One of the rare plains of the central district, its cultural texture is weak. When evaluated together with the places around it, it sits somewhere. A good place to de-stress with best friends. After a few laps, you question life. The place where the indispensable people of Dersim will be found."

Maurice Halbwachs (1992) *On Collective Memory* In his work titled, he discussed what kind of images an individual uses in the present to reconstruct his past. According to Halbwachs, human memory can only function in a collective context, and collective memory is always selective; various groups of people have different collective memories and different behavior patterns (Halbwachs 1992). These forms of behavior appear before us in Palavra Square with a political opposition, differentiation of official and local meanings. The people of Tunceli revived their social position as a way of collective understanding, leaving certain traces in the space. In this sense, it appears as a reproduced past through the relationship that memory proves with Palavra Square. On the basis of considering the collective memory of Tunceli from an everyday place like Palavra Square,

K4- "A street that smells good of history. The busiest place in Tunceli dates back to before 1980. Its former name is Republic Square. The square where cattle, old people and cars pace. They were beautiful places. Of course, he has to read a book to talk. He used to tell the books he read to the opposite groups as if he was giving a lecture in the bullshit square. It would be considered bullshit for those who didn't read it. Even if the square has a language, its experiences in it speak".

Pierre Nora (2006) defines the relationship that memory sets up with space, history as a trace of the past. Nora considers the spaces of memory in a context where tangible spaces share symbolic meanings. In line with the perspective of Nora (2006), there is an effort to make the monuments, events, historical architecture of the city, dictionaries, celebrations and ceremonies produced in a place with a certain historical, cultural and public meaning, such as Palavra Square, continuity in memory. In this sense, Palavra Square gains meaning both as a place and as a place where selves and identities are revealed in the process with its social aspect. Therefore, Palavra Square is the face of the social features that make up Tunceli.

Palavra Square as a Political Space

Squares are basically places where ideas are gathered and discussed. Until 1980, the squares were important socializing and discussion venues. Political processes, modernization, globalization, widespread vehicles, traffic density and shopping centers have put the squares in the background. The place known as City Square, Republic Square and Palavra Square among the people in Tunceli has undergone a momentous change

after 1980. Palavra Square appears as an area where marches were held before 1980, where people pull out their chairs and discuss daily politics, economy and politics. Meydan is a place where rumors, gossip, current developments and theoretical discussions continue in Tunceli.

K2- "Because the reading habit has just developed. When the readers exaggerated on behalf of their own group, other groups would reply as bragging to humiliate. They were setting up and destroying a state in the blasphemous square. Exaggerating the events of the people marching in this square. I think it's humorous. For being honest 'lie'. The place of exaggeration. Fun space"

K2- "As the leftist group was mostly in Tunceli, therefore, the most discussion would be in these places. Palavra Square was like a cultural center, a theater, a conference hall. It is understood as a symbolic place for Tunceli. It's a symbolic place. "P1- I heard that people from all left groups were having intense discussions and making analyzes about the left of the world and Turkey in this square. I can say that the reason it is called the square of bullshit is the source of the discussions and discourses of revolutionary people about destroying the order and building a new one. It is the most crowded sloping place in Dersim. The square is straight, our square is a little sloping".

K3- "It is the main street in Dersim square. The square where people wander and chat. Before 1980, very left-wing groups appeared in Turkey. However, much reading and heated debate began to take place. It's like a school. Of course, when there are arguments, the bullshit starts to get mixed up, so a bullshit square is formed".

Tunceli is the only province in Turkey where Alevism is not a minority belief. Alevis, who are generally defined as the other and minority in Turkey, are the majority in Tunceli. For this reason, culturally speaking ideas and political issues in the square show differences compared to other provinces. In the pre-1980 period, when there was a lot of political diversity, every left movement had a branch in Tunceli. One of the important opportunities of these policies to introduce themselves to the public is Palavra Square. People would meet in this square at all hours of the day and present their theories on foot with the effect of being a political city.

K4- "It is a busy square in the city center of Tunceli and used extensively by the people. I've seen and traveled many times. It is a symbolic space for the people of Dersim. I heard that in the 70's, the name of the square remained as "Palavra Square" because the revolutionaries who were in the square in groups bullied each other. It is a street with sentimental value for Dersim. The square in the market square. Everyone passes there".

The reason this square is called Palavra Square is because the image of intense debates and everyone defending their own opinion is called "lying". Lying is a story art. Ralph

Keyes says that gossip is especially important for community self-regulation (Keyes 2017). The basic discourse here is that the square creates a large socialization area, is used as a political space and will also be defined as a place of entertainment. The name of the square was reinforced by answering the question "what will happen, as if they are bragging" when asked what was said in the square.

The official name of Palavra Square is Republic Square. Palavra Square was also destroyed after 1980, when the squares were strictly forbidden to come together. The square is called the place where Cumhuriyet Street is found today. The place where the underground bazaar was built in the square began to be known as the City Square. Today, there are many businesses called "Bullshit" around the City Square and Cumhuriyet Street, where official ceremonies are held. In the past, parties from Ankara to the city held rallies in this square or politicians made speeches here. The politicians' failure to keep their promises in this square has popularized the name of "brag" among the people. This is one of the reasons why the people of Tunceli call this square "Bullshit Square".

Conclusion

Squares are a way of speaking of a society. Squares are places where society comes together and reproduces itself. Squares have been tried to be dominated by the government throughout history. Squares have a key role in the formation of public space. The public sphere plays a key role in building democratic societies. For these reasons, modernization efforts are conducted with the spatial transformation of squares. The politicians' saying the words they could not keep in the Palavra Square has led to the fact that it is called the bragging square among the people. Society sometimes resists oppression with rumors, mockery, nicknames. The constant talk of politics in the square and the boredom of the people again led to the definition of what is told here as "lie". Gathering here again, the fact that unreal stories are told as real and the atmosphere of rumor is created is one of the reasons for the name of this place. As a place produced after the 1950s, Palavra Square became quiet after the 1980s, but is still known as a place where people gather, talk and meet. Palavra Square, as a spatial reflection of Tunceli's dissident and witty people, can be defined as an embodied reflection of urban identity.

Source

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[1] Participants were coded as K1, C2, K3 and K4.

[2] It is a form of address in Tunceli. It is used in the form "Ma don't pass through here" in Tunceli, like "Don't pass through here" in Thrace, "Do not pass through here" in the Black Sea, and "Do not pass through here" in the East.